

ROBOTICS FOR FLIGHTLINE SERVICING

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ABSTRACT

The Flight Dynamics Laboratory is looking at the feasibility of using robotics on the flightline. The objective is to develop the capabilities and technologies to perform aircraft ground support functions more efficiently using fewer personnel. This will enhance future sortie generation capabilities by assisting ground crews in the preparation of mission ready aircraft. It will also encompass many types of fighters and transports in the Air Force inventory and will consider both fixed hangar and bare-base scenarios. The Laboratory is investigating ground refueling using aerial refueling tactics. This concept was selected as the initial turnaround candidate because of its frequency, impact on sortie generation, availability of hardware, and the fact that in-flight refueling receptacles are standard equipment on all tactical and strategic aircraft. This makes refueling ideal for robotics.

INTRODUCTION

For the past seventy years, military aircraft turnaround has been accomplished by ground crews of varying sizes who perform all servicing tasks manually. A target time of seventy-five minutes to completely turnaround an aircraft is the norm and this standard must be maintained to deliver an effective punch to the enemy. However, the use of chem/bio agents has been observed during recent wars, and this poses a threat to the traditional method of servicing aircraft. To perform aircraft turnaround tasks in a chem/bio environment, the ground crews must wear protective clothing or "chem-gear" as it is commonly called. The chem-gear impairs the vision, hearing, and dexterity of the crew members; builds up a great deal of heat stress; and is physically uncomfortable, especially during extreme weather conditions. This results in increased aircraft turnaround time and, unfortunately, occurs at a time when aircraft sortie generation is critical and available manpower is limited. A situation such as this makes addressing new methods of aircraft turnaround imperative for the Air Force.

This being the case, the Flight Dynamics Laboratory at Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, Ohio, initiated a program in 1986 to study the feasibility of using robotics to perform aircraft turnaround. The idea was not necessarily to replace our ground crews but rather to assist them in carrying out their flightline duties more

effectively during any threat. The program began with a contracted "Study of Robotic Concepts for Aircraft Turnaround" by the Battelle Memorial Institute of Columbus, Ohio. Battelle's work set the stage for the Flight Dynamics Laboratory to design and build its robotic capabilities to test these concepts.

AIRCRAFT TURNAROUND FUNCTIONS

Our research in this area started with an in-depth study of the turnaround process on a typical flightline. The dynamics of aircraft turnaround are explained below as they are shown in flow chart form in Figure 1.

When an aircraft is returning after delivering a sortie, the pilot relays the status of the aircraft to the ground crew in order to give them a head start on preparations for the turnaround. The plane lands and taxis to the de-arming area where landing gear is secured and wheels are chocked. The crew chief gives a thorough visual examination from outside paying special attention to the information deciphered from the previous radio message of the pilot. A determination is then made on the physical condition of the aircraft and its air-worthiness. If the aircraft has no damage, then it is taxied to the turnaround area where the following turnaround functions are performed:

- Oxygen service
- Load ammunition, bombs, missiles, and chaff
- Routine maintenance and checking fluid levels

Once these functions are accomplished, the turnaround process continues with the following functions:

- Refueling
- Wheels unchoked and aircraft taxied to end of runway
- Re-arming devices activated
- Aircraft is directed to runway to await take-off

If the aircraft appears to have minor damage, it is still taxied to the turnaround area where the minor repairs are performed concurrently with other turnaround functions stated above. However, if the damage to the aircraft is excessive, a further evaluation is conducted in order to find out if the

Figure 1 -- The Aircraft Turnaround Process

repair is time-effective. If so, the aircraft is maneuvered to a repair facility for conducting the needed repairs. Afterwards, the aircraft's status is upgraded to being air-worthy and it is brought on-line for turnaround services. If, however, the repairs are not time-effective, a further assessment is made to determine whether the repairs are cost-effective and whether the plane can be repaired. If it can, the marooned aircraft is moved into a storage facility for repair at a later date. But if the repair is not cost-effective or the aircraft cannot be repaired, then it can be scrapped for parts for use on other working aircraft.

USE OF ROBOTICS

The ultimate objective of this effort is to perform the previously stated turnaround process with the aid of robotics. Apparently, the individual turnaround functions require different levels of dexterity, varying crew sizes, and different times to complete. Introducing robotics may lead to the regrouping and/or rearranging of these tasks. Techniques may also vary to account for the state-of-the-art in robotics and the different combat aircraft in the present Air Force inventory. The approach will be modified in the future with the advancements in robotics and the design changes of next generation aircraft. It is hoped that future aircraft will become modularized and be more subject to repair and service by robotics. Assuming this trend, the use of robotics will be addressed under the three categories below.

- Present day applications
- Near-term goals
- Far-term concepts

Existing aircraft are not designed to be repaired or serviced by mechanization. However, robotics have advanced far enough where some simple, individual, and less involved tasks can be programmed to be performed by walking/traveling machines more effectively and accurately with a human overseer watching and controlling the operation from a distance, while enjoying the comfort and protection from the hazards of the operation and/or unpleasantness of the environment. The equipment for this has already gone through the laboratories and the technology is sitting on-the-shelf awaiting confidence of the user.

The near-term goals are envisioned to be completed in the next five to ten years. It can be safely assumed that no dramatic changes are expected in aircraft design and manufacture in the near term. However, small steps/modifications will be made on an individual basis to have better access to certain areas/components and these will be dictated by the user. Also, there will be great progress on the robotics front. Machines will be performing many single tasks with a remote human supervisor and performing some simple tasks autonomously. A few simple tasks will also be performed jointly by multiple robots with a common human supervisor.

Far-term concepts (i.e., beyond ten years) will require quite a few changes in aircraft design and

metallurgy. Special attention must be paid to component access and repair by robotics. Wherever possible, the approach will be to compartmentalize so that a unit can be easily pulled out and replaced by another unit. The replaced unit will be diagnosed and serviced by human technicians in the workshop. The units will become more solid state and computer chip design to better interface with the main controls. Far-term will see many developments in robotics for autonomous servicing and operation, and for coordination between different robots working simultaneously on the same aircraft while assisting or complementing each other's work. The human overseer will strictly think and design/develop software, plan out the work for each robot, and maintain the robots in working order for their turnaround duties.

ROBOTIC REFUELING OF AIRCRAFT

The Flight Dynamics Laboratory critically surveyed all tasks in the aircraft turnaround process such as inspection, routine maintenance, minor repairs, ammunition and missile loading, and refueling, and arrived at the conclusion that refueling was the best task to initially consider for automation. Refueling is the most commonly performed turnaround function and requires the least amount of dexterity, which makes it the most amenable to robotics. A further study showed that the in-flight refueling nozzle of a tanker aircraft like the KC-10 or KC-135 and the in-flight refueling receptacle on operational aircraft are ideal for remote/robotic applications. The in-flight refueling hardware is already proven and is standard equipment for the Air Force. This led to the idea of modeling ground refueling using aerial refueling tactics in a laboratory set-up.

The next question was which scenario a robotic refueler should service. The choices considered were:

- A bare base
- A hangar set-up
- An underground facility along the runway

A bare base is sometimes referred to as an austere or remote facility which is used in case of emergencies. Since there are no fuel hook-ups available, a refueler has to be mobile so that it can locate and re-orient itself near the aircraft, find the target (refueling receptacle), autonomously connect, refuel, disconnect, and move away from the aircraft. Development of such a refueler is envisioned for far-term applications. A variation of this device could be a one unit, truck mounted, telerobotically operated vehicle. This concept first appeared in IEEE, December 1986 [Ref. 1]. Another variation of this might be a refueling truck driven by a human operator who will drive it near the aircraft and an autonomous robot will do the rest.

A hangar set-up is a drive-through or tow-in facility. Robots might be mounted on a gantry framework on the top or sides of the hangar. With the help of sensors (namely vision), the robot could automatically locate an aircraft's in-flight refueling receptacle, compute the receptacle's

position with respect to its own position, proceed to refuel the aircraft, and return to a known or "home" position. This approach can be easily accomplished in the near-term with present robotic technology. Sensors and supporting software will have to be integrated with the robot for a workable final product.

An underground facility located along the flightline is very ideal. As an aircraft taxis along to the refueling location, sensors can observe its movements and direct the doors to an underground facility to open. From here, a refueler can unfold itself, automatically locate the in-flight refueling receptacle on the aircraft, make the connection to refuel, and move away to return back to the underground location. Such a concept is shown in Figure 2.

Of the three scenarios discussed, the underground set-up is the most practical and would meet safety requirements and regulations for the hot-pit refueling case (engines running). Although some of the technologies exist for this application, the integration of these components has not yet been accomplished.

LABORATORY SET-UP

In our laboratory set-up, we chose to mimic the hangar scenario with an overhead gantry. A 1/8 scale F-16 model rolls into the hangar and our laboratory robot, nicknamed FRED (Flightline Robotic Engineering Device), locates the in-flight refueling receptacle with its vision system. FRED computes the coordinates of the plane's in-flight refueling receptacle, picks up a refueling nozzle, and proceeds on an obstacle-free path to the model aircraft. Once its job is done, the robot returns the nozzle and goes back to its home position. Presently, FRED has one camera mounted overhead which gives a global view of the hangar area. It is in the plans to incorporate proximity sensors (ultrasonic type) on the forearm of FRED to judge the distance to any obstacle, stationary or moving, and to incorporate force and torque sensors so that FRED can exert a known force, or just the right force, so as not to damage the object gripped. FRED will also have a small camera on its shoulder for local viewing of the task being performed.

SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT

The theory behind developing the computer software to control our robot is to map out the hangar area from above to determine the exact coordinates of the in-flight refueling receptacle on the F-16 model. As the picture acquired by the camera appears digitized on the computer screen, coordinates of the model aircraft's in-flight refueling receptacle are computed for image tracking. As FRED moves towards the model aircraft, his position is constantly updated with new coordinates until it reaches the target. First generation software has been developed for imaging, mapping, path planning, navigation, and obstacle avoidance. Work is under way for making this software more sophisticated for real-time tracking which will enhance the path planning algorithm to incorporate the avoidance of moving obstacles and the integration of other sensors. Near-term plans include moving forward from two-dimensional to three-dimensional imaging.

CONCLUSIONS

Robotics for aircraft servicing is an ongoing program for the Flight Dynamics Laboratory. The present phase will have direct applications to aircraft refueling for hangar or overhead mounted robots. For the underground refueling efforts, the software needs to be modified slightly. Besides these direct payoffs, the in-house research also yields many software modules such as real-time imaging and tracking, path planning, collision avoidance, navigation, force feedback, and sensor selection. This work, when used in those wartime scenarios, will bring us a step closer to protecting our ground crews from exposure to hazardous environments. This will eventually improve aircraft sortie generation and sustainability by optimizing the time required to turnaround aircraft.

1 Schultz, Edwin R., "Robotic Systems for Aircraft Servicing," IEEE AES Magazine, December 1986, pp. 24-27.

Figure 2 -- Conceptual Underground Refueler